

THE ROLE OF WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE IN WORLD LITERATURE

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Abstract. *This article presents William Shakespeare's life and his works. The history of world literature is difficult to imagine without Shakespeare. His influence on the development of theatrical art is immeasurable. His tragedies were ranked among the masterpieces of world literature. Shakespeare's works are still coming from the world stage today without falling. Despite so much effective work and fame, William Shakespeare did not receive any awards, nor was he awarded a diploma.*

Keywords: *history, literature, culture, translation, imagination, sonnets.*

РОЛЬ УИЛЬЯМА ШЕКСПИРА В МИРОВОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлена жизнь Уильяма Шекспира и его творчество. Историю мировой литературы трудно представить без Шекспира. Его влияние на развитие театрального искусства неизмеримо. Его трагедии были причислены к шедеврам мировой литературы. Произведения Шекспира до сих пор сходят с мировой сцены без потерь. Несмотря на такую результативную работу и известность, Уильям Шекспир не получил ни одной награды, не был удостоен и диплома.*

Ключевые слова: *история, литература, культура, перевод, воображение, сонеты.*

William Shakespeare (c.1564 - 1616) was an English playwright and poet. He is recognized as one of the greatest exponents of English literature and, perhaps, the most famous author in the entire history of mankind. Shakespeare's fame is thought to have overcome the obstacles of time that no writer has ever seen. Works like *Romeo and Juliet* they are part of the popular imagination of Western civilization and continue to be represented all over the world. Shakespeare settled in London in the late 16th century. There he began his adventures in the theatrical world, as an actor and writer for one of the local companies known as "Lord Chamberlain's Men", which later used the name "King's men". Not much is known about his life, since faithful biographical notes have not been preserved. However, it is known that he had a wife named Anne Hathaway, with whom he gave birth to three children, Susanna, Hamnet and Judith.

As for Shakespeare's work, it is like an endless ocean, its drift is not seen. Shakespeare's literary legacy consists of poetry and drama. The epics "*Venus and Adonis*" (1593) and "*Lucretia*" (1594) related to Roman history, which he wrote on the basis of a mythological plot, were warmly welcomed. These works, especially the "*Sonnets*" written in the years 1592-1600, showed that Shakespeare appeared in an integral relationship with the culture of the Renaissance. Shakespeare effectively used Holinshed's "*Chronicle of England, Scotland and Ireland*", rich in plots related to the history of England, in creating his dramatic works. Plutarch's "*Comparative Biographies*" in the creation of Shakespeare's historical tragedies, and M. Bandello's accounts of the Italian Renaissance served as a primary source. Based on the plots of such tragedies as "*Romeo and Juliet*", "*Hamlet*", "*King Lear*", stage works were created even before Shakespeare. But these plots, due to Shakespeare's great dramaturgical skill, served as a vital source in the

creation of immortal works expressing universal thoughts and ideas. The quality that illuminates all of Shakespeare's work is the depiction of high moral and spiritual problems. "Romeo and Juliet" is lyrical, "Julius Caesar" is political, "Hamlet" is an intellectual tragedy, and "Othello" is a tragedy of passions. ethical issues of great importance for the time lie. If the dramatic conflict described in works such as "Julius Caesar", "Hamlet", "Macbeth", "Romeo and Juliet" allowed the characters to know themselves and realize their spiritual strength, then the mind of lost characters such as Othello and Lear is inevitable only when a tragedy occurs. only when doom approaches does it become radiant. Nevertheless, each of them and the heroes of Shakespeare's works in general are basically strong and courageous people with a strong character, a well-formed mind and moral views, a watchful eye on reality. The discovery of Shakespeare by the Uzbek audience began in 1935 with the staging of the tragedy "Hamlet" at the Hamza Drama Theater (now the Uzbek National Academic Drama Theater). After that, in Uzbek and Russian theaters in Uzbekistan, Shakespeare's Othello, Romeo and Juliet, Julius Caesar, King Lear, Coriolanus, Two Boys from Verona, The Casting of a Squirrel Girl, Strange Horses on a Summer Night such works were staged with great success. Gafur Ghulam, Yashin, Uygun, Shaikhzada, Turob Tola, Q. in translating Shakespeare's works. Writers and translators like Mirmuhamedov took part. Shakespeare's sonnets were translated into Uzbek by Yusuf Shomansur, Jamal Kamal and Khurshid Davron. In recent years, Jamal Kamal directly translated Shakespeare's works from English into Uzbek. The translation of "Hamlet" written by Cholpon is a prime example of Uzbek translation art .

Shakespeare's contemporary and researcher French Merez wrote about the poet's lyrics in 1598: "As the ancient Roman linguist Epius Stalo said, if the muses (fairies of inspiration) knew Latin, they would have spoken only in the language of Plautus. "If they spoke English, they would use Shakespeare's beautiful phrases in their speech." It turned out that Shakespeare's contemporaries, who were literary snobbers, had great respect for the poet's lyrics. The basis of Shakespeare's lyrics are his sonnets. The sonnets of the poet aroused the interest of readers and attracted the attention of scientists while still in manuscript form. In 1609, the publisher Thomas Thorpe published them for the first time under the name "Shakespeare's sonnets". The Sonnets were not published again during Shakespeare's lifetime. Even the book "Shakespeare's Comedies, Chronicles and Tragedies" published in 1623 did not include sonnets. Only in 1640, the poet John Benson collected Shakespeare's sonnets and republished them in a book holiday. According to John Benson, by this time interest in Shakespeare's sonnets had waned, and they were overshadowed by the love lyrics of John Dunne, who became a popular poet of his time. The reason is that the Renaissance (awakening) literature in 17th century Europe ended its life with the work of its last great poet, William Shakespeare, and gave way to a new type of sharia.

By the 18th century, interest in the great work of Shakespeare was revived. Renowned scholar George Stevens republishes Shakespeare's 1793 works. The famous English romantic poets S.T.Coleridge and J.Keats revived Shakespeare's legacy. Samuel Coleridge, who lectured on Shakespeare's legacy and his place in English literature, praised the "musicality and sweetness of the poet's lyrics", while John Keats said that "I have never read Shakespeare's sonnets with a fuller and more lyrical mood." ” he praises.

During the last 20th century, many scientific and critical works dedicated to Shakespeare's sonnets were created. The writer's sonnets were translated into world languages. For example, more than twenty translators of poets tried to translate Shakespeare's sonnets into

Russian. The translations of V. Bryusov and S. Marshak are close to the original and have been published over and over until now. The talented poet Yusuf Shamaqsud translated Shakespeare's sonnets into Uzbek from the existing versions of the Russian translation. Sonnets in Uzbek language were published in a separate book "Holiday".

While reading Shakespeare's sonnets, we observe that the philosophical depth, priority of lyricism, high mood and musicality in their content captivate the reader. The lyrical hero, that is, the poet, openly declares his loyalty to his tall, handsome friend, Mr. W.H., and his love for the black-haired, wheat-faced lady. It is interesting that Shakespeare scholars are still puzzled over the solution of the inscription on the title page of the book "Sonnets" that says "I wish happiness and long life to my mysterious friend, Mr. W.H., who was the main reason for the writing of these sonnets." Who was the faithful friend of the poet who kept a secret, and who was the "dark-haired, wheat-faced" lover whom he described. Incidentally, hundreds of articles and studies have been created on Shakespeare's sonnets. Masters of words such as Goethe, Wordsworth, Oscar Wilde analyzed them. However, none of them could tell the name of the dear friend whom the poet was hiding.

Shakespearean scholars interpret the writer's sonnets mainly in two parts. The first part includes the sonnets from 1 to 126, that is, the author's sonnets dedicated to his "mysterious friend", and the second part, from 128 to 152, that is, the sonnets dedicated to the "dark, wheat-faced lady". So, most of the scholars say that in the sonnets belonging to the first part, Shakespeare described his close friend and patron Earl of Southampton, while others tried to prove the poet's younger contemporary Earl William Herbert (W.H. these letters correspond to his name in English). In any case, the desire of the young, sympathetic and mallasoch described in sonnets is hot it is clearly felt that this young man is close to the poet's heart. As described in sonnets, the poet goes away from a sympathetic guy for a certain time and follows a "brunette lady", while the young man goes to a meeting of other poets in the form of an unclean. The poet's heart, whose heart finally faded to the brunette, again makes a strong friend, mallasoch, yearn for the young man, humbly addressing his beloved with jealousy:

O, call not me to justify the wrong

That thy onkindness Leys upan my heart...

This 139th sonnet was turned by Joseph Shamansur as follows:

Pinhonki in the verb dishonor, lie

Do not force to justify cancellation...

Ultimately, the poet rejects the unfaithful and frivolous brunette lady, who is dishonest in love, and puts her devotion to her dear friend above him. The two secret friends will be together again, regaining their previous secretly relationship. In conclusion, the accent part of Shakespeare's sonnets in content praises the confession of the lyrical hero on the path of reverence, and, so to speak, the prayer of recovery. The rhyme of Shakespeare's sonnets ab ab cd cd ef ef is in the form of gg, the richness of verses in metaphors and aphorisms, the mastery of philosophical meaning are visible.

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